

LEADERSHIP OF EDUCATIONAL IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT (MBS) IN MADRASAHS THROUGHOUT WEST SUMATRA PROVINCE

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Abstract

Official decentralization was carried out again by the Indonesian Government through Law No. 22/1999 which was later revised into Law No. 32/2004 brought changes in school management, namely School Based Management (MBS) which involves the role of schools and school committees in making every school policy and decision. One important aspect of MBS is the school principal leadership model implemented. One leadership model that is relevant to MBS is transformative leadership which has the characteristic of trying to change situations. Transformative leadership principles are simplicity, motivation, facilitation, innovation, mobility, readiness, and determination. Transformative leadership, if applied to educational institutions, namely schools, and Madrasahs, will significantly contribute and influence to these educational institutions' progress. The transformative leadership style is very important to be implemented in school and madrasah educational organizations, especially in implementing the MBS pattern which emphasizes participatory, transparent, and democratic management.

Keywords: Leadership, Madrasahs, School-Based Management.

INTRODUCTION

Since the implementation of decentralization on January 1, 2001, the education system in Indonesia has begun to establish a MBS pattern, better known as MBS. MBS, a translation of "School-Based Management", represents a call for the implementation of decentralization and regional autonomy policies (Bjork, 2003). The enactment of Law No. 32/2004 regarding Regional Government and Law No. 33/2004 concerning "Central and Regional Financial Balance" has led to significant transformations in various aspects of life, particularly in the realm of education (O'dowd, 2004). This law gives Regencies/Cities governments the authority and freedom to administer all areas of life, including education. The authority given by the Central Government to Regional Governments gave birth to policies of decentralization and autonomy, namely the authority of regional governments to regulate their own regions by prioritizing the central government as central of governance.

The application of MBS of course also applies to Madrasahs. With the shift in administration from centralized to decentralized, formal educational institutions are anticipated to autonomously chart their course and establish policies for managing their institutions. Consequently, educational establishments are obligated to engage in healthy competition, striving to enhance the quality of education based on the unique characteristics of the school, its environment, and the available capabilities.

Madrasahs as schools with Islamic characteristics have their characteristics, namely their curriculum, methods, and ways of teaching which are different from schools (Anshori, 2021). Even though Madrasahs also teach general science as taught in

schools, Madrasahs have their character, namely that they emphasize the religious values of their community. An essential determinant for the efficacy of school, and Madrasah-Based Management (MBM) is the professionalism of the principal. The pivotal role of the school principal is highlighted, particularly in the era of MBS or MBM. As a proficient educational administrator, the principal bears full responsibility for the outcomes of the school under their leadership. Research indicates that the performance disparity between high-achieving and low-achieving schools is attributable to the impact of the school principal (Mohammadpour & Shekarchizadeh, 2015).

The MBS/MBM era with its autonomy provides opportunities for school principals to develop leadership values (Anwar et al., 2019). In this era full of change, various challenges and threats that come and go require a firm attitude and intelligence to seize opportunities and plan for the future. Therefore, leaders who are appropriate to the conditions, namely having a commitment to quality and always updating it according to the demands of stakeholders (Das et al., 2008).

One type of leadership that should be considered in the MBS/MBM pattern is transformative leadership. This is because, in transformative leadership, the role of teachers and other staff in educational institutions can be actively involved, so that MBS/MBM is not interpreted as principal-based management, but means school-based management. In this regard, Leithwood & Jantzi (1990) stated that the presence of a transformative leadership style has great potential to build a high level of commitment in teachers to address the natural or traditional legacy of complexity and uncertainty in schools. Having transformative leadership capacity will also facilitate efforts to accelerate the growth of teachers' capacity to develop themselves to respond positively to the school reform agenda.

In line with the opinion above, Visionaries state that transformative leadership exists to answer the challenges of an era full of change (Huse, 2003). This article discusses the meaning of educational leadership, the MBS concept, and transformative leadership in madrasa-based management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Educational Leadership

Leadership in MBS/MBM plays an important role, especially in overcoming the challenges of school principals in creating opportunities for effective meetings with teachers in a conducive environment. The principal's behavior must encourage teacher performance by demonstrating the qualities of friendship, closeness, and attention, both at the individual and group levels.

George R. Terry defines leadership as the act of influencing people to voluntarily work towards common goals. According to the Encyclopedia of Administration compiled by lecturers at the UGM Center for Administrative Development, leadership is characterized as a process of influence among individuals or groups in a specific situation, facilitated through directed communication to achieve predetermined objectives (Xiong et al., 2022).

As defined by the Decree of the State Civil Service Administration Agency No. 27/KEP/1972, leadership is the act of persuading individuals to actively participate in a task. According to the Circular Letter of the Head of the State Civil Service

Administration Agency No. 02/SE/1980, leadership is the skill of a civil servant to persuade others for their optimal deployment (Yamin et al., 2018).

From the opinions above, it can be concluded that leadership is an effort to move other people or those being led to work together towards a goal that is mutually desired and considered important. Three important points that characterize leadership are the leader, followers, and context or situation toward achieving goals.

Key aspects of leadership include 1) guiding behavior in directing activities; 2) managing power relationships with team members; 3) supervising the communication process to achieve certain goals; 4) fostering interaction between personnel to achieve certain results; 5) initiating activities to uphold job satisfaction and; 6) involved in organizational initiatives to improve performance, and so on (Latham, 2014).

Educational leadership encompasses all efforts to influence individuals within the educational environment in specific situations. It involves fostering a collaborative environment where individuals willingly work together with full responsibility and sincerity to achieve predetermined educational goals.

In the progress of educational institutions, educational leadership has two main functions (Schlechty, 1990): 1) increasing the effectiveness of educational organizations by fostering a strong work ethic and efficient management, recruiting teaching staff with high standards, encouraging the development of teaching staff as good role models positive, providing constructive feedback to students, ensuring favorable working conditions for teaching staff and administrative staff, delegating responsibilities to students, and encouraging collaborative activities between educators and students; 2) strive for the success of educational institutions/schools by prioritizing curriculum implementation as the main goal, prioritizing the quality of teaching and learning, setting clear goals, high expectations for both teaching staff and students, fostering a positive, conducive, organizational climate, combining monitoring and evaluation as an integral component of the institution's educational culture, managing staff development, and garnering support from stakeholders for its overall development.

School Based Management Concept

The SBM concept originated in the United States, emerging when there was increasing attention to the alignment of education with the needs and progress of local communities (Spillane & Kenney, 2012). SBM represents a contemporary paradigm in educational administration, providing significant autonomy to schools and encouraging community involvement within the framework of national education policy. This management approach functions as a strategic initiative to grow effective, efficient, and productive schools (Ghani et al., 2020). SBM embodies a form of educational decentralization, empowering each school to develop in accordance with the authority delegated to them.

MBS is a model of independent educational governance, providing great independence to schools with a focus on increasing effectiveness, efficiency, and productivity to improve the quality of education (Dones et al., 2023). This approach aims to facilitate schools in providing better and more adequate education for students. Management autonomy empowers schools to improve staff performance, involve relevant stakeholders directly, and foster increased public understanding of education.

In line with the principles of decentralization and autonomy in the field of education, school/madrasah authority also plays an important role in accommodating the existing consensus that wherever possible decision-making should be in the hands of those with the best access to local information who bear responsibility for policy implementation, and directly affected by this policy.

As an operational form of educational decentralization within the framework of regional autonomy, SBM is expected to be able to have an impact on increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of school/madrasah performance, by providing educational services that are comprehensive and responsive to community needs. With school-based management, it is hoped that it can also increase efficiency, participation and quality, as well as being responsible to the government and society. Some characteristics of madrasa-based management are (Sofanudin & Rokhman, 2016):

First, granting broad autonomy to Madrasahs provides broad autonomy to Madrasahs, accompanied by a series of responsibilities for managing resources and developing strategies according to local conditions. Madrasahs are also given broad authority and power to develop curricula and learning programs by the conditions and needs of students as well as community demands, as well as explore and manage funding sources according to priority needs.

Providing broad autonomy to Madrasahs makes them able to accommodate the needs of local communities in managing their Madrasahs, including in their curriculum and learning. For example, Madrasahs emphasize local content in speech training, because local communities need preachers and religious figures who can spread the message of Islam.

Second, high community and parent participation requires the implementation of madrasa programs that are supported by high participation from the community and parents. Parents and the community not only support Madrasahs through financial assistance, but through madrasa committees and education boards they can formulate and develop programs that can improve the quality of Madrasahs.

This participation from the community and parents also makes it easier for schools to accommodate their aspirations and desires regarding the management and development of Madrasahs. It is not uncommon to find community and parent participation apart from thinking, but they are always willing to help the madrasah if needed. In order to foster a strong connection between the madrasah, the local community, and the parents of the students.

Third, democratic and professional leadership. School principals and teachers as the main actors in the implementation of education in Madrasahs are figures who have professional abilities and integrity. The madrasa head is a professional education manager who is selected to manage all madrasa activities based on established policies. Madrasah teachers are educators who work based on a mutually agreed professional performance pattern to provide convenience and support student learning success.

Fourth, Team work which is compact and transparent. The success of madrasah programs is of course supported by the performance of a compact and transparent team from various parties involved in education at the madrasah. The madrasa head, teachers, madrasa committee and madrasa education board jointly carry out their

respective duties and responsibilities in order to realize the madrasa goals to be achieved.

Transformative Leadership

The concept of transformative leadership consists of two elements: leadership and transformative. The meaning of leadership has been discussed previously. The term transformative means the act of changing or transforming something into another, different form. For example, the transformation of vision into reality, heat into energy, potential into actuality, latent into real, and so on. Thus, transformative refers to qualities that can change something into another form, such as changing potential energy into actual energy or changing achievement motives into real achievements (Frediani, 2010).

Transformative leadership essentially refers to a leader's ability to collaborate by effectively changing organizational resources to achieve significant goals in line with predetermined achievement targets (Schiuma et al., 2022). These resources may include human resources, facilities, funds, and external organizational factors.

Transformative leadership, which was initiated by Burns as the originator of this term, is a process in which leaders and followers elevate each other to a higher level of morality and motivation (Shields, 2011). This involves ongoing interactions in which leaders and followers inspire each other to increase levels of morality and motivation with respect to their primary tasks and functions. This leadership style has the potential to increase follower awareness by encouraging the generation of productive ideas, enhancing synergistic relationships, instilling a sense of responsibility, showing concern for education, and sharing the same ideals and moral values.

From this perspective, transformative leaders are characterized by foresight and commitment to improving and developing the organization not only for the present but also for the future. Such leaders function as agents of change and serve as catalysts, playing an important role in steering the system toward improvement. They aim to elicit reactions that generate enthusiasm and rapid action, and consistently position themselves as innovators and facilitators of change (Ellsworth, 2000).

According to Covey and Peters, transformational leaders have a clear vision, maintaining a comprehensive understanding of how the organization will appear in the future once all its goals and objectives are realized. Transformative leaders view organizational values as noble principles that must be codified and determined collectively by staff, fostering a sense of ownership and commitment among them. The leader's responsibility is to translate the organization's values to facilitate the realization of the organization's vision. A transformative individual is someone who possesses diagnostic skills, consistently investing time and attention to address problems from multiple perspectives.

Based on the insights of leadership experts and transformative leaders, it can be concluded that school principals are considered transformative leaders when they are able to transform human resources, tools and situations to meet school reform goals.

Considering the perspective of teacher well-being, school principals can be considered implementing a transformative leadership approach if they effectively carry out the primary responsibility for transforming energy within teachers, moving from latent energy to real energy, from potential to actual, from minimal to optimal, and from formality to actuality. Viewed from the perspective of students' interests, a

transformative leadership style has proven to be useful in efforts to utilize children's cognitive potential into real achievements, turning potential skills into practical achievements, and so on (Mulford, 2008).

Bass and Aviola highlight four important dimensions in the level of transformative leadership (McCarley et al., 2016): 1) Ideal Influence which involves respectful behavior and self-confidence from the leader towards his team. Ideal influence includes the idea of sharing risks by prioritizing staff needs above personal needs and demonstrating ethical moral behavior; 2) Inspirational Motivation, reflects behavior that consistently challenges staff in their work and emphasizes the importance of their tasks. Leaders demonstrate commitment to organizational goals through observable behavior, acting as motivators who continually inspire staff enthusiasm and optimism; 3) Intellectual Stimulation, focusing on leaders who embrace innovation. Their leadership attitudes and behaviors are rooted in knowledge development, which enables them to translate intellectual insights into productive performance. As an intellectual, the leader actively explores new ideas and creative solutions from staff, consistently encouraging a culture of learning and the application of new approaches to work and; 4) Individual Consideration, showing that the leader is an attentive listener who follows up on complaints, ideas, hopes and all input provided by staff.

Therefore, transformative leadership can be studied from a micro and macro perspective. At the micro level, it is seen as a process of influencing individuals, whereas at the macro level, it involves the mobilization of forces to bring about change in social systems and institutional reform.

Transformative Leadership and Transactional Leadership

Discussions about transformative leadership are always linked to transactional leadership. Bass and Avolio argue that the concepts of transformative leadership and transactional leadership models are similar to the concepts of leader and manager models. In this sense, transformative leaders always emerge in crisis situations, times of change, and are always developing. Meanwhile, transactional leaders work in a more mechanistic bureaucratic situation, which tends to favor status quo conditions.

Even though transformative leaders and transactional leaders have the same role, namely working to achieve predetermined goals and objectives, they both have different strategies in carrying out functions and motivating subordinates. Transformational leaders are leaders who are able to lead their subordinates towards a higher and more dynamic consciousness. A boss who practices transformative leadership is seen as a "leader" not a "manager" or according to Garder is called a "lead manager" and not a "routine manager". This discourse describes the profile of someone who plays a transformative character (Cowie & Cornelius, 2003).

Transactional leadership is a leadership style that prioritizes the tasks carried out by subordinates. In this context, a leader is someone who designs work and its mechanisms, while staff are individuals who are tasked with carrying out these tasks based on their abilities and expertise. This leadership approach is suitable for implementation among less experienced staff, because it emphasizes completing tasks to gain incentives rather than self-actualization. Work systems are clearly defined and rewards are aligned with the level of effort put into the task (Colvin & Boswell, 2007).

On the other hand, transformative leadership is different from transactional leadership. This is not solely based on fulfilling self-esteem needs but also instilling awareness in leaders to achieve, in line with research in the field of management and leadership development which views individual growth, performance and organization as interconnected aspects. Transformative leaders motivate their staff or subordinates to go beyond their current abilities, with the goal of achieving immediate personal gain while collectively realizing the organization's vision and mission. The following are the differences between transformative and transactional leadership behavior in table 1.

Table 1: Differences between transformative and transactional leadership behavior (Pieterse et al., 2010).

Transformative	Transactional
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change the situation • Change what you usually do • Talk about lofty goals • Has a reference value of freedom, justice and equality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • work in situations • Accept limitations • Accept existing rules and values • Reciprocity and bargaining

Principles of Transformative Leadership

The emerging transformative leadership paradigm includes seven main principles: 1) Simplicity, where effective leadership begins with a vision that becomes a common goal and guides reflection. The crucial skill lies in articulating a clear, practical and transformative vision that answers the question “where are we going”? an important element in implementation; 2) Motivation which means the ability to guarantee the commitment of all parties involved to the vision that has been explained. Leader transformative not only creates organizational synergy but also optimizes, motivates, and energizes each follower; 3) Facilitation, demonstrating skills in effectively facilitating learning that occurs within the organization at the institutional, group, or individual level. This contributes to increasing intellectual capital everyone involved; 4) Innovation, which involves the ability to be brave and responsible to encourage change when necessary, aligning with evolving needs; 5) Mobility, namely the mobilization of all available resources to empower and fortify individuals in achieving vision and goals ; 6) Preparedness, highlighting the ability to remain open to independent learning, accepting positive changes with new paradigms; 7) Determination, describing an unwavering determination to complete a project, emphasizing the need for spiritual, emotional, and physical discipline and commitment in supporting this determination (Caldwell et al., 2012).

Effective Principal Leadership

The study of transformative leadership types is something new when compared to other types of leadership. Therefore, at a practical level in the field, not many organizational leaders apply this type of leadership. The same thing also happens in educational organizations, be they schools, Madrasahs and Islamic boarding schools.

However, even though it is new, there has been a lot of research conducted that shows the effectiveness of transformative leadership to be applied in organizations, including educational organizations. A study conducted by Leithwood & Sun (2012) resulted that a transformative leadership style contributed to restructuring initiatives, and in the opinion of teachers contributed to improving student learning outcomes. However, this contribution is mediated by other people, events, and organizational

factors, such as teacher commitment, teacher job satisfaction in the workplace, and school culture which have a positive influence on school organizational restructuring initiatives and improving student learning outcomes. Therefore, transformative leadership has a transformational focus on teachers as the spearhead of the learning process.

An empirical study conducted by Roeser et al (1996) shows that mediating variables and school culture play an important role in fostering positive feelings among teachers towards their work and motivating students to learn. This study further confirms that a positive school culture is correlated with increased student motivation and achievement, increased collaboration between teachers, and positive changes in teachers' attitudes toward their future work. The quality of the classroom learning experience—whether interesting or monotonous, conducive or deviant, productive or deviant, enjoyable or boring—is largely influenced by teachers' attitudes toward their responsibilities. This positive attitude, according to research, does not stand alone but is partly influenced by the principal's transformative leadership style. Through a transformative leadership approach, the potential of learning organizations can be realized effectively in achieving institutional goals.

The results of the research above and other research show how urgent it is to implement this type of transformative leadership in school organizations. This is mainly because transformative leadership is able to fulfill the main requirements in the SBM work format which requires participative management. Thus, the tradition of school leadership as a single leader must be abandoned, and then adopt an integrated leadership style of shared leadership.

To achieve this, school principals are required to become human learners who are willing to change towards improvement. Here are some tips for leaders to start implementing a transformative leadership approach as proposed by Barling et al (1996), namely: 1) Make decisions transparently and consistently. This will encourage respect and trust; 2) Demonstrate and encourage an enthusiastic and optimistic attitude, so that teachers and staff become more confident and inspired to do better; 3) Condition and invite teachers and staff to always look at problems in the work environment from a clear perspective, so that it will encourage teacher and staff participation in decision making; and 4) Taking time to pay attention to teachers and staff, for example by giving awards to teachers and staff through internal meeting forums.

Changing the leadership style towards transformative leadership is like an adventure for the progress of the school, for this reason the principal must be able to play an important role such as (Montuori & Donnelly, 2017): 1) Breaking away from traditional leadership work styles; 2) Stimulate the participation of the learning community; 3) Stimulate teacher commitment to grow professionally; 4) Encourage the participation of teachers and school staff in leadership processes.

The following are several indicators of a school principal's transformative leadership developed from the four dimensions proposed by Bass: 1) Being a very dominant figure in the school; 2) Involving teachers in planning an activity; 3) Involve yourself in all aspects of school activities; 4) Generating a sense of mutual respect for the opinions of fellow colleagues; 5) Treat others with respect; 6) Sacrifice personal interests for the sake of the group; 7) Be an inspiration; 8) Make staff ready to sacrifice personal interests for the good of the group; 9) Make the people around him

enthusiastic about working; 10) Generating loyalty to the organization; 11) Show confidence in staff opinions; 12) Request feedback from staff regarding the results of their work; 13) Encourage teachers to express their ideas and opinions; 14) Increase teachers' feelings of optimism towards the future; 15) Give awards if teachers complete their work well; 16) Give appreciation for staff work in the form of personal praise; 17) Attend various meetings and seek various sources of new ideas and convey them to staff; 18) Looking for new ideas by attending other schools; 19) Just getting to know individual teachers is enough to know their skills, interests and understand the problems they face; 20) Eliminate punishment for mistakes as an effort to professionalize and improve schools; 21) Determining the boundaries of differences flexibly, providing freedom of opinion and action as long as it is within the framework of school policy; 22) Encourage staff to always evaluate work results and improve them; 23) Solve old problems in new ways; 24) Encourage staff to try new ways in various activities; 25) Increase staff motivation for success and; 26) Encourage innovative, hardworking and professional staff (Hauserman & Tongkat, 2013).

The leadership performance of school principals in the context of SBM/MBM includes all efforts made and results achieved by school principals in implementing SBM/MBM in their schools to achieve educational goals effectively and efficiently. The effective leadership of a school principal at MBS/MBM can be assessed based on the following criteria (Minarti et al, 2022): 1) Ability to empower teachers to carry out the learning process effectively, smoothly and productively; 2) Completion of assigned tasks and responsibilities on time; 3) Establishing harmonious relationships with the community to actively involve them in realizing school and education goals; 4) Successful implementation of leadership principles that are in line with the maturity level of teachers and other staff in the school; 5) Collaboration with the management team and; 6) Productively achieve school goals in accordance with established provisions.

CONCLUSION

In Indonesia, the study of transformative leadership is still relatively new, although not completely new. Thus, it is very natural that at a practical level in the field not many schools and Madrasahs implement this type of leadership. However, along with the increasing challenges and demands in the world of education, a transformative leadership style is very important to be implemented in school and madrasah educational organizations, especially in implementing the MBS pattern which emphasizes participatory, transparent and democratic management.

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